

A Research on Privatization of Military Logistics Services and Outsourcing in Nato's Logistics Activities

Askeri Lojistik Hizmetlerinin Özelleştirilmesi ve Nato'nun Lojistik Faaliyetlerinde Dış Kaynak Kullanımı Üzerine Bir Araştırma

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ABSTRACT

With the end of the Cold War, the United States and other Western armies undertook substantial reforms. Armies, which had previously performed various tasks with their own organs and were capable of fulfilling them everywhere due to their organic structure, have now sought ways to reduce and exploit external resources to partially fulfill their tasks. The reorganization of NATO member countries' military logistics systems included strengthening and modernizing efforts against new threats emerging after the Cold War. While many NATO members, primarily the Turkish Armed Forces, continue to cooperate with the private sector to strengthen the country's defence industry, the idea of purchasing services from outside sources has gained importance due to changes in public procurement legislation in recent years. Our study aims to investigate the potential benefits of outsourcing logistical functions to external sources and their influence on the trend of using external resources. In order to achieve this goal, a survey of officers and officers serving at the NATO staff level measured and interpreted the potential benefits and trends in the use of external resources based on a study of literature and experience. The study aims to scrutinize the political, legal, economic, and ethical aspects of private military companies, and pinpoint potential areas of collaboration with the Turkish Armed Forces. In this context, the primary focus of the study is to determine the areas where the Turkish Armed Forces should utilize external resources, and to explore how private military organizations can effectively fulfill NATO's military logistical service requirements. In addition to previous studies, this research has the potential to raise global awareness about the importance of private military companies.

Keywords: Military Logistics, External Resource Use, Private Military Company

ÖZET

Soğuk Savaşın sona ermesiyle birlikte Amerika Birleşik Devletleri ve diğer batı orduları önemli ölçüde reformlar gerçekleştirdiler. Önceden kendi organları ile her türlü görevi yerine getiren ve kendi organik yapısı ile her yerde yetmeye imkân ve kabiliyeti olan ordular, görevlerinin bir kısmını dış kaynaklardan elde etmek için küçülmenin ve dış kaynaklardan yararlanma yolunu aramıştır. Soğuk Savaş'ın ardından ortaya çıkan yeni tehditlere karşı teşkilatlanma ve modernizasyon çalışmaları, NATO üyesi ülkelerin askeri lojistik sistemlerini yeniden düzenleme sürecini içeriyordu. Başta Türk Silahlı Kuvvetleri olmak üzere birçok NATO üyesi ülke savunma sanayinin güçlendirilmesi için özel sektörle işbirliği yapmayı sürdürürken, son yıllarda kamu ihale mevzuatında yapılan değişiklikler nedeniyle dış kaynaktan hizmet alımı fikri önem kazanmaya başladı. Çalışmamızın amacı, lojistik işlevlerin dış kaynaklardan sağlanmasının olası faydalarının dış kaynak kullanımı eğilimi üzerine etkilerini incelemektir. Bu amaca ulaşmak için NATO tugay seviyesinde görev yapan subay ve astsubaylara uygulanan bir anket çalışması, literatür incelemesine ve tecrübelerine dayanan olası faydaları ve dış kaynak kullanımı eğilimini ölçmüş ve yorumladı. Siyasi, hukuki, ekonomik ve etik açıdan özel askeri şirketleri incelemek ve Türk Silahlı Kuvvetleri ile ortak çalışma alanlarını belirlemek. Bu bağlamda, çalışmanın temel sorunu, Türk Silahlı Kuvvetleri'nin dış kaynakların hangi alanlarda kullanılması gerektiği ve özel askeri kuruluşların NATO'nun askeri lojistik hizmet ihtiyaçlarını kesintisiz nasıl karşılayabileceğidir. Araştırmanın, daha önce yapılan çalışmalara ek olarak, özel askeri şirketlere dikkat çekmek konusunda dünya çapında farkındalık oluşturma potansiyeline sahip olması da onu önemli kılmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Askeri Lojistik, Dış Kaynak Kullanımı, Özel Askeri Şirket

1. MILITARY LOGISTIC

NATO defines military logistics as the systematic process of strategizing and executing the movement and sustenance of armed forces. Logistics, in a broader sense, refers to the military system responsible for the planning, creation, provision, storage, transportation, distribution, operation, and disposal of military equipment, as well as the provision of services and support for health services,

among other things. (NATO Logistics H.B, 2012.) NATO has categorised logistics into two distinct groups: Production Logistics and Acquisition Logistics. Production Logistics encompasses the activities of researching, designing, developing, producing, and accepting materials. According to NATO, it includes elements such as standardisation, contracting, quality assurance, reliability, defence analysis, safety standards, production processes, coding, documentation, and configuration control. Consumption logistics, also known as operational logistics, focuses on the management of product acceptance, storage, delivery, maintenance, and handling. It also involves the efficient handling of materials, stock control, construction and operation of facilities, movement control, adherence to reporting standards, and training. (NATO Logistics Handbook, 2012:43).

Military logistics is the process involving the planning, production, supply, distribution, maintenance and replacement of equipment and materials to support military operations. It can also be defined as the art of keeping the material needed to the success of the operation ready where requested, at the requested time, in the desired condition. Military logistics is the process involving the planning, production, supply, distribution, maintenance and replacement of equipment and materials to support military operations. It can also be defined as the art of keeping the material needed to the success of the operation ready where requested, at the requested time, in the desired condition. The place of military logistics in the military system in war and peace, which is "the systematic performance of activities such as the main system, equipment, storage, transportation and distribution, and evacuation required to carry out military operations effectively and efficiently at the desired place and time" (Koçak, 2020). It has been discussed since the 19th century.

Military logistics is discussed in French military theorist Antonie Henry Jomini's work *The Art of War* and in Prussian military theorist Carl van Clausewitz's *On War*. Antonie Henry Jomini defined logistics as a field that covers all military activities other than war (Eraslan, 1968: 2). Jomini examined the theory of war in five categories: strategy, major tactics, logistics, intelligence, and tactics. Jomini defines logistics as "the art of moving orders." (Jomini, 2013:14). He expressed logistics as a discipline with suggestions that cared for and adopted its place in the war, although it was not clearly defined. Jomini said that victory would be won by a commander who acted and planned in accordance with the military logistics, demonstrating the troops' ability to confront the enemy in an orderly and violent manner. (Jomini, 2013:355). In the 19th century, another famous military thinker, Carl Van Clausewitz, often mentioned himself, saw logistics as a necessity for the realization of absolute destruction, the ultimate goal.

Clausewitz defined logistics as a tool for achieving a goal, emphasizing that war is more important. (Clausewitz, 1991:544-548). Although Clausewitz underestimated military logistics as part of the war, he explained his theory of absolute destruction in a much clearer way than Jomini did. (Juniar & Duarte, 2005:645-647). According to one of the war theorists of the modern world, Thorpe, the military logistics that we face on the issue of the region's dependence on military needs, such as human and animal power, weapons and ammunition, etc., has become a "business" with World War I. Thorpe noted the importance of logistics in warfare, which he described as strategy, tactics and logistics, as a force that could invite the army to disaster and defeat. He described logistics as a consciousness-creating branch of war that coordinates warfare. (Folk, 1986:15-18).

Moshe Kress said that the continuity of military operations has seen military logistics in every period of history, and emphasized the awareness of its importance, while stressing that the fact that intelligence in the modern world order also supports military logistic is irrefutable. Strategic-tactical, intelligence and military logistics cannot be dealt with separately or independently. (Kress, 2002:6).

Military logistics, a critical component of military operations, must be carefully planned and managed to meet the needs of military forces. Military logistics, which represents the supply, transportation and delivery of the resources that soldiers need during a war, is crucial in terms of winning wars or successfully conducting military operations. Military logistics, one of the key

elements of many military operations from the past to the present, has had a direct impact on the achievement of the objectives of the military operation. The most important elements of the military logistics concept, which contains many items, are (Özkan vd., 2015: 73-77)

Transport Systems: Transport systems may include intermodal systems that combine road, rail, air and maritime transport as well as different modes of transport.

Storage and Distribution Centres: Storing and distribution centres are used to store and distribute facilities, materials and equipment containing many elements from food and water to ammunition and spare parts.

Supply Chain Management: Supply chain management involves the management of equipment and materials, as well as the monitoring and distribution of these items within the military logistics network. **Communication and Information Systems:** Communications and information systems are used to coordinate and direct the flow of information and materials within the military logistics network.

Maintenance and Repair Facilities: Maintaining and repair facilities are used for repair and maintenance of a wide range of materials and equipment, from vehicles to weapons.

Medical support: Medical support includes providing medical care and equipment to military personnel, as well as transportation and treatment of wounded soldiers.

1.2. External Resource Use in Military Logistics Activities and Private Military Companies

Today, globalisation has arisen from the interconnection of transportation, telecommunications, and information systems that span over nearly the whole globe. The pervasive impact of intensifying and constricting competition has compelled organisations to exercise greater prudence in managing costs, given its influence on all economic and military endeavours. Following the conclusion of the Cold War, significant alterations have occurred in the United States and other Western military forces. The armies, which previously relied solely on their internal organs to perform all functions and were self-sufficient in meeting their needs, have now been exploring methods to outsource and streamline some of the functions they have internally accumulated by utilising external resources. (Acar, Ateş:2011)

External resource utilisation, a widely adopted practice in the past two decades, involves concentrating solely on one's core competencies and delegating specialised tasks to experts in those areas. The utilisation of external resources is predominantly restricted to mundane tasks such as sustenance, safeguarding, and sanitation. However, we are now intending to employ external resources in all activities, with the exception of their fundamental functionalities. (Harris,2006) The defence and security industries have been significantly impacted by the neo-liberal economic paradigm since the 1980s.

Private military enterprises have commenced offering the essential logistics, training, planning, and infrastructure services required by the armed forces. The outsourcing of military bases and facilities, vehicle maintenance, clothing and equipment supply, and storage, administration of military hostels, and operation of canteens has been delegated to the private sector through the main loader system. (Matthias,2012;204) Operation Desert Storm, the wars in Iraq and Afghanistan exemplify the utilisation of foreign resources for logistical support. Contractors have played a crucial role in providing combat service support to the American Army during operations and wars. Given that numerous logistical operations in the military sector are also performed in the commercial realm, these functions are the most probable choices for external use. The U.S. Army has implemented a significant overhaul of its logistics framework to effectively execute extensive missions. However,

this transformation has not only altered the institutional framework of the U.S. Army, but it has also revolutionised the corporations that function within the United States Army.

The evolution of the military logistics system has necessitated the integration of novel ideas and business principles. In order to achieve this objective, the concept of outsourcing logistics operations, establishing partnerships with global suppliers, ensuring direct sales, and utilising electronic commerce has been introduced. (Alabarda & Lisowiec,2007;22) The advancement of technology and weapons systems necessitates the armed services to possess a versatile and adaptable infrastructure capable of swiftly transitioning from peacetime to wartime. The primary advocates for the creation of this adaptable and versatile infrastructure have been the utilisation of external resources in a competitive manner and major corporations.

The United States Army's Logistic Civil Augmentation Programme (LOGCAP) bolstered battlefield operations by engaging private corporations through contractual agreements, thus serving as a crucial component of the Land Force. Furthermore, this approach allows for the prompt fulfilment of the military's urgent requirements by leveraging external resources. Additionally, it enables fruitful partnerships with reputable and sizable companies. The chosen primary contractors have offered robust logistical assistance to the U.S. Army in both peaceful and war settings. External resource uses in the military field can be given as examples of catering services, cleaning and bathing, entertainment, construction, laundry services, operating the base area, security, communications and maintenance. (Cardinali, 2001:107).

The Royal British Army says the 9,000 troops to be recruited every year will be carried out in the form of external resource use, including military recruitment and training phases. In broad terms, outsourcing firms can be classified into four distinct groups. The following will be presented: Private combat corporations are organisations that are at the forefront of military operations, directly engaging with the enemy and commanding regular troops. An exemplary instance is the renowned British "Gurkha Security Guards," who provided assistance to the Sierra Leone army at their headquarters in 1995.

Private security businesses offer specialised people to safeguard base areas, installations, convoys, and individuals. An example of a recent occurrence is the American-based corporation "DynCorp", which is responsible for providing security for Afghan President Hamit Karzai. Advisory firms are companies that provide guidance and advice to the armed forces of nations regarding various aspects of military knowledge and training. An exemplary instance is the American-originated "L-3 MPRI", which provided training to Croatian officers in 1995. Specialised Logistics Support Companies provide a range of services including washing, eating, consignment services, as well as delivery, storage, maintenance, and more. This group comprises companies that possess logistical expertise. For instance, the KBR (Kellogg Brown & Root) serves as a contractor for numerous logistical operations carried out by the US and British military forces. (Neil J. Haris, s. 14-5.)

The significance of establishing the institutional architecture of the system is contingent upon the specific requirements it must possess. In order to achieve this goal, the main contractor system has been implemented in countries that follow liberal economic policies. The purpose is to establish an institutional infrastructure that can facilitate the supply of manufactured products at the lowest possible price in competitive markets. This system aims to promote the development of original and advanced technology, particularly in the defence and security sectors.

In European countries, the defence industry is expected to contribute significant capital, investments, skilled personnel, high-quality products, and expensive tests, alongside technological advancements. State support is provided to companies in the pre-selected national main contractor position within the defence industry sub-sector. Each country has a national mainloader for the sub-systems of the defence sector, including tanks, planes, armoured vehicles, and electronics. The current

mergers taking place in Europe are intended to establish a prominent contractor within the European Union, rather than maintaining national parent contractors that operate solely within their own country. Therefore, in the context of exports, it aims to establish prominent and robust companies, particularly those capable of rivalling American corporations. Exclusive responsibility for the procurement of essential technologies, system integration, testing, and maintenance for the whole lifespan lies with national contractors.

1.2.1. Private Military Companies

Following the 1960s, the demand for military instruction for the national armed forces of pro-Western minor nations resulted in the rise of private military corporations. This was initiated by British and European retired soldiers who specialise in military training. (Cullen, 2008:240). David Stirling, the creator of the British Private Air Service (SAS), established "Watchguard International" in 1965, making it the inaugural private military business. The game "Top War" (Top War, 2020)

In the 1980s, following Britain's example, a proliferation of tiny enterprises in the United States emerged, giving seminars on combat tactics. Private military corporations in the United States have provided their services to the military, but British companies have mostly promoted their services to foreign nations. Although private military corporations achieved limited success in nations like the Congo in Africa during the 1960s, their overall influence on fighting was insignificant. (Singer, 2008:21-24). The ramifications of the bipolar security framework throughout the Cold War era hindered their ability to assume a dominant position. However, the security challenges that emerged during the Cold War prompted the establishment of the private military sector, which is spearheaded by private military companies.

Private military companies are exempt from specific regulations due to their lack of integration within national armed forces. This implies that their personnel are exempt from the military protocols and regulations that are often imposed on professional soldiers. Consequently, it prohibits private military corporations and their personnel from being penalised for actions that are beyond the jurisdiction of the government. State-controlled military personnel are bound by specific ethical regulations. Conversely, an employee of a private military firm relies on a company that offers higher salary than the government and naturally provides a source of financial support. Due to the prioritisation of financial gain, ethical regulations are disregarded. The practice of transferring military troops from one state to another under military norms is uncommon. However, it is widely acknowledged that the personnel of private military corporations are employed by numerous distinct entities. As an illustration, Wes Batalona, a forty-eight-year-old individual who was employed by four Blackwater private military organisations and died in Felluce in 2004, had prior experience working in other private military firms. Prior to joining Blackwater, Battalona was employed by private military firms such as DynCorp International and Military Professionals Resources, Inc. (MPRI). (Prince, 2013:110-111). The crucial distinction is in the contrast between individuals who are part of the national army and those who are not affiliated with the army. The actions of individuals who are enlisted in the military have legal implications for the government, whereas the actions of civilians do not impose any legal responsibility on the government.

The objectives of these companies, which operate in numerous zones of conflict worldwide, are nearly indistinguishable. However, these companies serve purposes beyond military operations. They work in a diverse range of industries. Aside from engaging in military combat, they also offer fundamental defence services, such specialised safeguarding for individuals, security for military harbours, oil fields, and convoys. (Keser, 2020). According to Peter Singer, military corporations can be categorised as "passive" or "active" based on their actions (Singer, 2008:89). Companies engaged in direct military operations, such as EO, Blackwater, and Wagner Group, encompass military firms like MPRI, which delivers training in field defence and advisory, and SADAT, which provides consulting and logistics services. However, this classification lacks scientific rigour. These

organisations primarily engage in activities such as active military operations, as well as passive consultancy, logistics, and supply services.

1.2.1.1.Utilisation of Private Military Companies

The inadequacy of international law in imposing effective limitations, along with the increase in regional wars, has provided the foundation for the emergence of the war economy. Therefore, the regions that have been severely damaged by the conflict are now subject to an industry that is controlled by economic factors rather than strict regulations. (Barrie, 2005). Private military enterprises are prominent in this market. Following the conclusion of the Cold War, nations have progressively diminished their military forces in order to mitigate the financial burden of maintaining compulsory personnel. Between 1987 and 1996, the United States and Russia, who were the leaders of two opposing ideologies, decreased their military forces by almost six million troops (Maciąg, 2019). Consequently, this implies that a total of six million soldiers will be rendered jobless. Given the situation in other states, it is not challenging to anticipate that the number will be at least double. However, as the number of troops has decreased, the frequency of confrontations has grown in an inverse relationship. During the Cold War era, a total of 13 United Nations Peacekeeping Forces were established to be sent to areas of conflict. However, by 2023, this number had increased to 71. The year is 2023 and the United Nations Peacekeeping mission is underway.

Globally, there has been a significant increase in the number of private military companies operating today. These companies are global players that operate in every aspect and on every continent. (Kinsey, 2006). Private military companies are private companies that sell military services, including war, consultancy and logistics. Private military companies are companies that provide special services related to conflict and war, including war operations, strategic planning, intelligence collection, operational and logistical support, training, supply and maintenance. Registered enterprises with corporate structures as their organizational structure.

2. THE NATO MILITARY STRUCTURE AND WORKING BODIES

Within NATO, all 31 member states possess equal rights to express their opinions. The decisions made by the Alliance are unanimous and rely on a shared consensus. Furthermore, the members of NATO uphold and honour the core values of the alliance, which include democracy, individual freedom, and the rule of law. Before NATO makes a significant decision, lengthy negotiations are typically necessary to get the support of all members and guarantee that the choice respects the sovereignty of each Ally. This is the procedure by which all the Allies unite in support of NATO when NATO decides to take action. The North Atlantic Council (NAC) is the main political decision-making body of the Alliance. The Council and its affiliated Committees provide the Allies with a framework for consultation, co-operation and planning on political and military actions. The Council meets at the level of Allied ambassadors once a week and more frequently if necessary.

The Council also holds regular meetings at the level of Foreign and Defence Ministers. NATO holds summits every year or every two years, where the Allied Heads of State and Government take decisions on strategic challenges facing the Alliance. Regular meetings are also held with representatives of NATO partners. At NATO Headquarters in Brussels, each Allied country has a permanent representative at ambassador level. The Representative shall be assisted by a national delegation of diplomatic personnel and defence advisers.

The meetings of the Committee are attended either by delegation members themselves or by national experts. The political dimension of the decisions taken is implemented through NATO's civilian headquarters in Brussels, Belgium. Military dimensions are implemented by the NATO Military Committee under the political supervision of the Council. This committee is in contact with the Allied Operations Command, which is located at the European Allied Forces Headquarters near

Mons, Belgium, and the Allies Transformation Command in Norfolk, Virginia, USA, and has a NATO Secretary-General appointed every four years. The Secretary-General is a senior politician of one of the member countries. The Secretary-General chairs meetings of the North Atlantic Council and other important NATO bodies, seeks consensus among members and serves as the Alliance's chief spokesman. The Secretary-General is assisted in the conduct of the Alliance's day-to-day work by international staff consisting of experts and officials from all NATO members.

3. IMPORTANCE of LOGISTICS ACTIVITIES FOR NATO

It has gained greater importance with the increasing intensity of NATO's off-regional operations in the Balkans, especially after the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989 and after the 9/11 attacks on New York. While there are different options for operational applications, the continued logistical support of all troops involved in all operations, regardless of which model is chosen, is the responsibility of the NATO Commander. The basic principles of NATO Logistics, which have been applied without exception since the Cold War, have been expressed as “Logistics support is a national responsibility” and have been defined as follows: Customer responsibility, Authority, Operational priority, Coordination, Safe forecast supply, Adequacy, Activity, Flexibility, Traceability and Transparency. (MC, 2009:64). Following the Welsh (2014) and Warsaw (2016) summits, where significant resolutions were made about NATO's deterrent and defensive position, the Alliance has bolstered, hastened, and broadened its scope with the inclusion of Montenegro into the alliance.

This position provides the Alliance with numerous strategies to address the increasing number of threats to the Allies' territory, which have nearly doubled since the end of the Cold War. The rise in the number of Allies has also brought attention to certain instances of the distances that the deployed forces will encounter. Currently, NATO has a limited but strategically positioned presence on its eastern border, which can be promptly reinforced as required. The reinforced Advance Force, comprised of four multinational combat groups stationed in Poland and the Baltic States, consists of a combined total of 4,500 men from Allied nations who possess the ability to collaborate effectively with national defence forces. The bilateral US presence under the framework of the European Disarmament Initiative provides assistance for all of these efforts.

Furthermore, certain initiatives in the Black Sea region have bolstered NATO's deployment on land, at sea, and in the air. At the Brussels Summit (2018) the Allies also endorsed the NATO Preparedness Initiative. The initiative guarantees that highly qualified, combat-able and highly prepared national forces can be handed over to NATO.

The Allies will be able to put 30 fighter ships, 30 manoeuvres, and 30 aircraft fleets in service from the general force pool, which can reach readiness in 30 days or less. This initiative will further strengthen NATO's ability to respond rapidly in order to strengthen the Allies or to intervene militarily quickly in a crisis. However, there are many dimensions of the rate of replenishment of multiplied advanced elements. It's not just about the level of preparedness of our forces. Providing timely supplementation also depends on other factors: the ability to make quick decisions based on indications and warnings for a hybrid campaign, supported by adequate intelligence; and factors such as pre-planning and preparation, and the ability for NATO to use and manage the huge forces (including those from beyond the Atlantic) to be assigned to its command. All these areas have been strengthened by NATO since 2014 to secure the Alliance's position and to make it more capable, credible and up to date.

3.1. Utilisation of External Resources in NATO

With the first 10 years of the millennium behind NATO, significant changes have taken place in the logistics sector, depending on global developments. Within the context of the post-Cold War NATO transformation, the concentration of non-Article 5 operations, the reach of strategic dimensions (about 10-15,000 km), the rapid growth of information technology over the network base

and the logistical support of multinationals executed operations which is more than an adversary to filling the battlefield, the logistics transformation that began with logistics dominating in the same field of action, uncoordinated, recurring, exhausting and consuming resources in an unnecessary competition, has affected all the underlying branches of logistics. In this context, logistics transformation in NATO (Keskin, 2011:694)

From a military approach to a comprehensive, scientifically supported approach, from static to flexible, from reactive to proactive, from regionality to globalization, from bureaucracy to networked capabilities, from dual-point logistics to integrated logistics, from national responsibility to collective responsibility. National responsibility and control in the logistics sector, as it used to be, is now replaced by the use of external resources and a collective, multinational approach with high visibility and capacity for action in a field where third-party action has begun to appear. Throughout the Cold War, NATO directed its attention towards Central Europe and strategically positioned its conventional forces along Germany's eastern border as a response to the Soviet threat. The Field Commanders were assigned distinct geographical duties and possessed a comprehensive understanding of the demarcations between forces and wing formations, potential conflict zones, communication protocols, and agreements established with the respective host countries.

The national forces extended rearward, towards the ports, and established fortified zones known as maritime corridors across the entire continent of Europe. This posture would facilitate the expeditious transportation of goods from North America to Europe through the North Atlantic. Extensive preparations were made, including the essential arrangements, infrastructure, military stockpiles, transportation capacity, and very comprehensive plans. By engaging in consistent training and activities at all levels, the capacity to collaborate efficiently was cultivated. Following the collapse of the Berlin Wall in 1989, the perceived danger emanating from the Eastern bloc was deemed to have ceased. Consequently, the Alliance decided to withdraw its forces, decrease the frequency of large-scale exercises, and shift NATO's focus towards the Alliance's "extra-territorial" missions.

The North Atlantic Council, which serves as NATO's primary political decision-making entity, would determine the specifics of operations, including the location, timing, and manner of execution. Following this decision, military planning would be executed, similar to the practices observed during the Cold War, instead of immediately implementing the existing defence plan and deploying troops. The 2014 Ukraine conflict heightened the Alliance's apprehensions regarding a resurgent and belligerent Russia. In this scenario, it became crucial to promptly fortify a vulnerable Allied nation within NATO territory, in order to discourage a potential adversary and safeguard the Allied nation from an assault, if prevention proved unattainable. Moreover, the presence of conflict and the increasing occurrence of terrorism in Syria, together with cyber-attacks on the Allies and other types of hybrid warfare, have brought attention to the possibility of conflict in both domestic and international arenas. This emphasises the significance of cooperation in terms of preparedness and resilience. Evidence has demonstrated that the Alliance must possess the capability to engage in a wide range of activities, including collective defence, crisis management, fostering stability in regions outside our boundaries, and helping to counterterrorism efforts. Consequently, there has been a shift in the current era, with a rise in both risks and obligations.

War is not a discipline that yields positive and definite results. According to Baron de Jomini, a prominent figure in the development of modern military thinking, logistics encompasses nearly all military operations apart from actual combat (1838). During that period, Jomini considered logistics to be "the deliberate skill of military forces" encompassing all the necessary tasks of supplying and managing armaments, including planning, provisioning, housing, constructing bridges and roads, as well as conducting exploration and gathering intelligence for manoeuvres outside the battlefield. Today, NATO's objective is to eliminate obstacles to the exchange of military information among

European and North Atlantic countries, and to empower its armed forces to carry out operations in the field within these regions.

For this purpose, there are four specific areas of focus: implementing measures and laws to make crossing borders easier; establishing effective command and control systems to conduct logistical operations; ensuring the capacity to transport military units and all their equipment; and developing infrastructure capable of handling significant quantities of heavy military assets. Within NATO, this extensive undertaking is known as "Activating the Area of Responsibility of the Allied European High Commander". The term "military" is a concise and accessible way to refer to components of this extensive programme. The simplification of border crossing authority and legislation inside countries and the European Union facilitates efficient communication, particularly during times of peace. Countries, the European Union, and NATO are collaborating to synchronise all plans, protocols, and methods, including diplomatic and other transit permits, in order to facilitate the smooth movement of troops and equipment across European borders, minimising delays and minimising impact on civilian life.

The command-and-control structures of the Alliance will work together with key civilian actors in each country to facilitate the movement of a significant number of military forces to, within, and outside of Europe. During the Brussels Summit, the leaders of NATO agreed to strengthen the NATO Command Structure by incorporating logistical elements at all levels. This will ensure that the necessary units and equipment can be efficiently replenished in manoeuvring formations. As part of this, a Command will be established in Norfolk, USA, to facilitate fast and secure refuelling from America to Europe. Additionally, a Customer Support and Activation Command will be set up in Ulm, Germany, to ensure smooth operations. NATO also encourages its Allies to develop their military capabilities and facilitate multinational and mass access to their transport capacities through pre-contracts with the European trade sector. In fact, NATO is facilitating this process, increasing its effectiveness, and simplifying methods by offering allies opportunities to combine resources and acquire customer capabilities.

The European Union, on the other hand, is taking encouraging steps in this direction with its plans to allocate more funds to defence investment. NATO is collaborating with the EU and other stakeholders to guarantee that transport infrastructure, including ports, roads, and bridges, adheres to the requisite standards, which will also be employed in domestic and possible EU projects. Without the cooperation of the European Union, it is impossible to overcome all of this workload. The two organisations are collaborating to eliminate obstacles to military intelligence operations in Europe. The European Union plays a crucial role in enabling the movement of military soldiers and equipment within Europe, as well as ensuring that the continent's transportation infrastructure is sufficient for the transportation of military force and heavy military equipment. NATO and the European Union have recognised the military-related matter as the foundation for their collaboration. In June 2018, Secretary-General Jens Stoltenberg emphasised the significance of the interconnection between the security of NATO allies and EU member states. He highlighted the necessity for the defence efforts of both organisations to be founded on cooperation.

This understanding was formalised through a declaration signed by European Commission President Jean-Claude Juncker and European Council President Donald Tusk. This implies the existence of three tiers of integration. Within NATO, research is being conducted on combat capabilities and characteristics that facilitate logistics, considering the understanding that logistics can have military, civilian, and economic implications. It is necessary to train all the parts that have the potential to contribute, and they should be trained collectively under simulated battle situations. This approach can also be referred to as "learning on the job." Furthermore, a holistic government strategy is suggested to address an extensive array of hybrid threats at the national level.

This strategy should additionally encompass the provision of assistance to civilian authorities and the harmonisation of the necessary resources for military deployment. Intergovernmental coordination is necessary to guarantee that allies possess the ability to function effectively during a crisis or conflict. During the Warsaw Summit, the Heads of State and Government of the Allies made a commitment to enhance resistance by focusing on civilian readiness. At the multinational level, efforts are being made to enhance cooperation between NATO and the European Union in order to effectively safeguard the Euro-Atlantic region from possible adversaries and promote the right dissemination of security and stability.

When examining the contracts the Western country's armies have concluded with private military companies, it shows that a wide range of services are provided, ranging from training, intelligence, the protection of personnel and bases, transportation, procurement, reconstruction and maintenance, to active combat and the provision of complex technology (GULAM, 2005:18). However, the extent to which such a wide range of services are provided suggests that torture and similar incidents can occur in the example of the Ebu Gureyb prison (Schwartz, 2010:16). Therefore, in order to avoid similar situations, it would be appropriate to use services provided primarily by private military companies to NATO Forces in areas outside intelligence and operational activities or, in other words, in logistical activities.

NATO is trying to comply fully with its existing logistics system, but this leads the commanders to concentrate almost exclusively on logistics. The commander is responsible for almost everything that occurs in the square, from the eating of the food of the soldier, the means of transport by which he will go to the trail or to the freight, the periodicity of the military vehicles, to the appropriation of the expenses. It is clear that it will be quite difficult to focus on the combat mission in such a complex structure.

4. CONCLUSION

The changing security environment in the international system also changes the security needs of the actors. Alliances, like other international actors, need to update their security insights and develop appropriate strategies to meet the needs of the security environment. NATO has changed and developed its strategies to meet different security needs that have emerged at different times. NATO's strategic concepts and institutions, its operational capabilities, have been shaped and revised to reflect the changing global political and security conditions since its establishment in 1949. After the collapse of the Soviet Union and the break-up of the Warsaw Pact, the Alliance's door was opened to the European Iron Curtain countries by means of an open-door policy, which sought to enlarge NATO to cover all of Europe. All European countries except Malta, Austria, G. Cyprus, Sweden and Finland have been ensured to be members of the Alliance. With the development and strengthening of the nation states, the concept of "national army" has become widely accepted. However, in parallel with the debate over what is "military", many states appear to diversify their armed forces by adding them to the army under different legal status. Therefore, in international politics or security-related developments, not only armies in the classical sense, but also units such as semi-military (paramilitary-paramilitarian) forces or private military companies need to be taken into account.

When it comes to international resources, it includes research into the relationships of the armed forces of developed countries with private military companies. As far as local sources are concerned, there is little research on how the armed forces collaborate with private military companies, but there are limited data on how these units will be carried out. The literature research section contains a number of studies on the use of external resources for civil enterprises. If we compare the findings with the data from the literature study, we can see that many of the data are consistent. But as military logistics has its own critical aspects, we see that some aspects are gaining even greater importance in military logistic.

It was concluded that outsourcing in the field of military logistics would be beneficial in terms of focusing on core activities, cost efficiency, saving human resources, saving time, reducing risks in military logistic processes, decreasing the workload of the armed forces' logistic components, providing flexibility in the choice of resources, specializing in military Logistics activities, providing employment to civilian logistics firms, and building military capabilities for civil logistic firms. While literature scanning is similar in many respects to the benefits it will bring to civilian logistics companies, focusing on real activities and cost effectiveness, rather than providing a military competitive advantage, is a priority. Civilian enterprises may also close outsourced logistics departments, while military logistics is expected to reduce the burden and increase flexibility of military logistic components, even if externally driven. However, military logistics, along with outsourcing, will add military capability to civilian logistics companies.

When we look at the disadvantages of externalization in the field of military logistics, different issues have emerged. It has been found that intelligence may cause disclosure, create excessive dependence on external sources, result in non-operation under enemy threat, misappropriation can result in financial damage, difficulties in reaching sources in times of crisis, and damage to the reputation and image of the armed forces. The criteria to be taken into account in the field of military logistics are outsourced. No previous domestic research has found such criteria in the military field. When compared to research on civilian enterprises, we see that the reliability factor is primarily external in the military sector. External drainage in this area is considered a non-reliability factor. We also see that in the military field, detailed external contracts are gaining even greater importance.

However, it is not new that they use "supportive" forces to solve security problems when faced with security problems that they cannot cope with (the "regulated army" emphasis has been used to distinguish them from other armed forces). Thro history, states have tended to use unorganized institutions directly under the umbrella of their regular armies or the security apparatus, either through additional forces they have created within the country, or through direct and indirect aid they receive from outside. Under this framework,'supportive military forces' may be defined as armed groups established by the state in order to assume certain special security roles, although they are not in the chain of command control of the regular army. The term "army" stated above refers to the regular armies of states. It is a well-established practice for them to employ "supportive" forces to address security challenges that they are unable to handle on their own. These forces, often referred to as the "regulated army," are distinct from other military forces. Throughout history, states have typically utilised decentralised institutions that operate directly under the jurisdiction of their standing armies or security apparatus. This is achieved either by establishing additional domestic troops or by receiving direct and indirect assistance from external sources. Within this paradigm, 'supporting military forces' might be characterised as state-established armed formations that undertake certain security responsibilities, although not being under the direct supervision of the regular army's chain of command.

With the participation of eastern NATO members, the distances have grown considerably. For example, in the past, an American army convoy, which was going from the port of Rotterdam to the West German border, had to cross 500 kilometres and only one border. Today, it takes more than 2,200 kilometres of roads and five borders to get to Tallinn. In fact, during the Cold War, many European countries were on or near the front line; today, they are very far from that line. Many countries lack the necessary military logistical capacity to transport their troops from one point to another. So these countries have to take advantage of a small pool of civil transport companies. In a serious crisis, these companies will be out of business, transport lines will become impassable, and host and transit countries will find it difficult to respond to calls for help. Travelling in the opposite direction, including military dead and wounded or civilian refugees, will make the situation even more difficult.

Although the emergence of such auxiliary forces is due to the inadequacy of regular armies against internal or external enemies using uneven methods, they tend to turn into security structures that exceed their functions by changing the threat or becoming a useful tool over time. Thus, emergency security measures, including civil war or conflict, may become structures that tend to preserve the existence and power of the regime or the ruling group. The study suggests that NATO can focus on its original missions if external resources are used in the field of military logistics. In this context, it is estimated that externalization in military logistics will provide NATO with a more effective combat force.

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